

LIMNOLOGY AROUND (A MORE EXTREME) WORLD: HUNGARY

What about fire & water? Wildfire consequences on aquatic ecosystems.

David Cunillera-Montcusí¹

¹Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions Fellow, HUN-REN Centre for Ecological Research - Institute of Aquatic Ecology, Budapest, Hungary.

Email: david.cunillera@dcm.cat

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Wildfires are among the most studied disturbances from several perspectives and science fields (Wright and Bailey 1982, Díaz-Delgado *et al.* 2002). The relevance of wildfires in shaping or affecting earth ecosystems constitutes a natural disturbance, intrinsic to some systems but fostered by human activities in others (Bowman *et al.* 2009, Pausas and Keeley 2009, Kelly *et al.* 2020). Wildfire regimes vary among regions owing to climatic characteristics and fuel structure, and these variations increase fire frequency and intensity in areas with Mediterranean climates (Pausas 2004, Le Page *et al.* 2008, Pausas and Ribeiro 2013). However, these climatic characteristics are predicted to change globally with an increase in temperature coupled with a decrease in rainfall, particularly during the summer months (IPCC 2022). These conditions will promote wildfires by increasing their predicted frequencies, intensities, and extents (Turco *et al.* 2018, Pausas and Keeley 2021, Joshi and Sukumar 2021, Fernández-García *et al.* 2022).

Within the current context of global change, derived from both climatic alteration (IPCC 2022) and changes in human-environment interactions (for example, field abandonment, reforestation, fossil fuel usage, stockbreeding; Kelly *et al.* 2020, Pausas and Keeley 2021), it is imperative to comprehend and anticipate wildfire consequences in all ecosystems. Although terrestrial ecosystems

characteristics of the wildfire event itself, whereas the indirect impacts are related to the period following the fire that can last over days, months, and years (Minshall *et al.* 1989, Gresswell 1999). In this context, the term “direct effects” refers to the entrance of ash or smoke diffusion into surface waters (Bright *et al.*, 2016; Scordo *et al.*, 2021). Contrastingly, the term “indirect effects” refer to the secondary outcomes of wildfires that influence post-fire trends in aquatic communities (Minshall *et al.* 1997; Silva *et al.* 2016). These alterations that wildfires may engender in the short, mid, and long terms within a catchment are the primary factors contributing to their repercussions. As aquatic systems receive water from areas affected by fires, the consequences of wildfires are concentrated within the aquatic system (Pinel-Alloul *et al.*, 2002; Prepas *et al.*, 2009; Smith *et al.*, 2011; Rhoades *et al.*, 2019).

Overall, the indirect effects of wildfires can be summarised into five groups derived from vegetation loss and ash generation/input in the watershed (Minshall *et al.* 1989, McCullough *et al.* 2019). First, an increase in runoff after a wildfire is generally expected owing to watershed vegetation loss and soil impermeabilization by ash, which fosters flash floods and higher runoff (Vieira *et al.* 2004, 2011, Whitney *et al.* 2015, Pereira *et al.* 2016), but also the modification of habitats mosaic within the catchment (Kleindl *et al.* 2015). Second, vegetation loss, especially the canopy, will favour light incidence and, consequently, the rise in water temperature during the months or years following the wildfire (Minshall *et al.* 1997, Hossack and Corn 2008, Isaak *et al.* 2010, Mahlum *et al.* 2011, Rhoades *et al.* 2011, Cooper *et al.* 2015, Rodríguez-Lozano 2015, Rosenberger *et al.* 2015). Third, ash and debris entering the aquatic system will increase during wildfires, but mostly together with first post-fire rains. Such entrance will boost nutrient concentration (Spencer and Hauer 1991, Spencer *et al.* 2003, Bladon *et al.* 2008, Mast and Clow 2008, Smith *et al.* 2011, Mast *et al.* 2016), debris, turbidity and sediment transport (Bêche *et al.* 2005, Reale *et al.* 2015, Vaz *et al.* 2015). Fourth, the combination of light, temperature and nutrient increase will foster primary production and algal blooms during the months after a wildfire (Cowell *et al.* 2006, Klose *et al.* 2015). Such trophic changes will markedly reshape available resources, promoting a switch from allochthonous to autochthonous production (Cowell *et al.* 2006, Verkaik *et al.* 2013, Silins *et al.* 2014, Cooper *et al.* 2015, Klose *et al.* 2015). Finally, other groups of aquatic organisms will be also affected by the combination of previous consequences that will span all the trophic chain with bacteria (Ferrenberg *et al.* 2013), macroinvertebrates (Scrimgeour *et al.* 2001), amphibians (Hossack and Corn 2008, Muñoz *et al.*

Fig. 1 Images from a Mediterranean temporary pond impacted by a wildfire. From left to right images show the same temporary pond, located in North-eastern Iberian Peninsula before (spring 2012), right after (summer 2012) and few months after (spring 2013) the wildfire that burned the Empordà region in 2012. Mediterranean temporary ponds are aquatic ecosystems that can be impacted by both direct and indirect effects of wildfire with the direct burning of aestivating organisms such as Gastropods and the indirect posterior fire-pulse effect (see Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2019, 2021). Photos taken by Jordi Sala.

have received the most attention regarding wildfire impacts, aquatic ecosystems have remained relatively understudied to date (but see Bixby *et al.* 2015, McCullough *et al.* 2019, Cunillera-Montcusí 2020). Even though they have remained understudied, some of the first studies focusing on wildfire impacts on aquatic ecosystems date back to 1989 (Christensen *et al.* 1989, Minshall *et al.* 1989). These works sparked many others focusing on lotic systems (Mihuc and Minshall 1995, Minshall *et al.* 1997, Minshall 2003, Romme *et al.* 2011), but also on lentic ecosystems (Gresswell 1999, Scrimgeour *et al.* 2001, Pinel-Alloul *et al.* 2002, McCullough *et al.* 2019).

What are the effects of wildfires on aquatic ecosystems?

The extant body of evidence identifies two major effects from wildfires: direct and indirect. The direct impacts are related to the

2019), and fish (Beakes *et al.* 2014, Rodríguez-Lozano *et al.* 2016). These group responses can vary considerably in accordance with post-fire conditions (e.g., floods, droughts, and other fires). On one hand, they can lead to a strong decrease in abundance (Vieira *et al.* 2011, Whitney *et al.* 2015, Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2019). On the other hand, together with the rise in temperature and trophic resources some groups may be benefited concomitantly increasing their abundance (Mihuc and Minshall 1995, Minshall *et al.* 2001, Scrimgeour *et al.* 2001, Malison and Baxter 2010a, Beganyi and Batzer 2011, Oliver *et al.* 2012, Brown *et al.* 2013, Lewis *et al.* 2014, Verkaik *et al.* 2015, Venne *et al.* 2016, Robson *et al.* 2018). Such a bottom-up event can feed terrestrial ecosystems with greater insect emergence and the consequent increase in terrestrial predators in what is known as fire pulse (Malison and Baxter 2010b).

Despite the apparent congruence in the reported wildfire, the impacts of wildfires strongly depend on system characteristics and, therefore, on the ecological context (Bixby *et al.* 2015, McCullough *et al.* 2019). Wildfire impacts will not be the same in rivers, where post-fire floods can be a strong determinant (Vieira *et al.* 2011); or in permanent boreal lakes, where nutrient accumulation can lead to greater eutrophication and an increase in generalist species (Scrimgeour *et al.* 2001, Araneda *et al.* 2013, Lewis *et al.* 2014); or in temporary streams or ponds, where both wildfire direct (i.e. direct burning of aestivating organisms) and indirect effects are combined (Verkaik *et al.* 2015, Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2019, 2021). Such variability in the responses of determined habitats and organisms highlights the large number of questions that remain to be answered when considering the impact of wildfires on aquatic ecosystems.

Future global change scenarios highlight the increasing importance of wildfires across many ecosystems because of the rise in their frequency and extent (Pausas and Keeley 2021, IPCC 2022, Fernández-García *et al.* 2022). Such scenarios emphasise the need to further advance our knowledge regarding their impacts on aquatic systems (Bixby *et al.* 2015, McCullough *et al.* 2019). One key asset to further consider is the role that regional-scale connectivity may play in post-fire community recovery (Chittapun 2011, Banks *et al.* 2017, Robson *et al.* 2018, Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2021). The consequences that wildfires will have on the impacted part of the catchment will greatly rely on connectivity and recolonisation from non-burned areas, as some habitats, mostly shallow lentic systems, may rapidly recover their pre-fire physical characteristics (Beganyi and Batzer 2011, Bright *et al.* 2016, Cunillera-Montcusí *et al.* 2020). Metacommunity and metaecosystem perspectives constitute interesting frameworks from which to provide novel answers and expand our understanding of the potential impacts of current and future wildfires, both for lentic and lotic systems (Cid *et al.* 2020, Cunillera-Montcusí 2020). Overall, there is still a long road to follow to unfold the responses of aquatic organisms and ecosystems to wildfires and to incorporate both larger spatial and temporal layers in the assessment of their consequences. All these elements remain essential to confront the fiery future that is already here.

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